

ON THE ANALYSIS OF ETHNOTOPONYMS

Maftuna Safarova Zoir qizi

Teacher of Bukhara State University

Safarovamaftuna21@gmail.com

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Abstract: This article discusses the motives, reasons and etymology of clan and tribal names found in the territory of Bukhara region. the importance of ethnonyms in the formation of place names is expressed.

Key words: name, ethnotoponym, toponym, ethnonym, clan, tribe, naiman, thousand, katagon, burgut, mangit, yobu.

It is known that people have been in different social environments, political and economic positions since ancient times, and are divided into certain groups and classes depending on this social position. Such stratification and various concepts and ideas related to it are expressed in the language using certain words. In some cases, clans and tribes were named according to the social position of the person who founded them or was the head of the clan. For example:

a) ethnonyms denoting the group of people considered to be poor, poor, that is, low-class: bare-footed, bare-headed, bangi;

b) ethnonyms representing the group of people considered to be rich, wealthy, ruling, upper class: beklar, beklartop, rich, boybicha, darkhan, mirza, malikbachcha, begish, eshankhoja, shikhlar, jabu//jabga, qazilar, ataliq.

It can be seen that the names of the groups belonging to the upper class were given by themselves in most cases, while the name of the poor, lower class ethnos was given by the representatives of the upper class. Because in these names, in addition to the real situation, the shades of contempt, discrimination, and insult are expressed.

S.Otaniyozov cites some interesting ethnonyms related to the given motive among the Turkmen ethnonyms: boytokhum (rich egg, clan of the rich), bayat, bayindir (rich, statemen), on the contrary, algachik (barefoot), achikbash (without headdress), ach, achlar (hungry), bitli (those who are hungry), kenbeli (those who live in shanties), bavatan (widower, homeless).

In addition, we can observe that ethnoses are named based on their profession and occupation. A. Otajonova noted the occurrence of clan names such as Uychi, Damirchi, Kolalalla, Maryanla, Arkanchi, Tuyachi in Khorezm ethnonyms. According to S.Otaniyozov, there are more than 150 ethnonyms related to profession in the Turkmen language. These ethnonyms indicate that

the ethnos is engaged in hunting, cattle breeding, agriculture, trade, and various handicrafts.

Among our materials are the milkman, the hare-keeper, the deer-keeper, the walker, the barker, the plowman, the beaver, the window-keeper, the saddler, the catari, the caravan, the jomachi, the hunter, the mirishkor, the hunter, the saiot, the tevachi, the tonchi, the turgok, the camel driver, the bearer, the ungur, there are ethnonyms such as Shatyrchi, Shalikor, Karavul, which provide information about the profession and occupation of the ethnic group in the past. Below we will touch on some of these ethnonyms.

Baqirchi - mang'it qabilasining qoramang'it bo'limiga mansub urug'lardan biri. Baqirchi - paqir qadimiy turkiy tilda mis tanga, pul birligi (4 gramm hajmdagi) bildirgan. Baqirchi etnonimi misga ishlov beruvchi, undan buyumlar yasovchi ma'nosida kelgan.

Baydaqchi is the name of a clan opposite to the Akmangit section of the Mangits. It is known that flag-flag-flag is a genetic word. The flag is a piece of wood with a special silk hanging on it, and it is determined by which side the soldier belongs to. The ethnic name indicates that flag bearers came from this clan.

Bovurchi - Mongol khan Temuchin founded the middle court position in the 70s of the 12th century. One of them is bavoruchi, which means the person who deals with food and nutrition of the khan. It is known that this position is also known as bakovul, waiter. There is also the karabovur clan, which is a branch of the liverwort. The suffix -chi in the ethnonym means collective, group, gang. Mergan - a sniper in the division of bells, sniper; kenagas, kovchin, mangits contain mergan seeds. This ethnonym is мерган in the Turkic language, мepгeн in the Mongolian language is a hunter, a master shooter; derived from a word meaning wise, clever, skillful and referred to the activities of clan members.

Hunter, mirishkor, sayot - these ethnonyms are close to each other in terms of meaning. One of the Uzbek tribes is called a hunter. The meaning of the word can be seen from the meaning of the word. The word Mirishkor is a special position in the khan's court, and the person who holds this position was engaged in the hunting activities of the khan, i.e., he served as a huntsman.

B.Kh.Karmisheva also points out that the emergence of the ethnonym "mirishkor" is related to this type of training.

Turkic ethnonyms include the ethnonym sayad//sayyot//sayyotlar. This ethnic group is part of the Uzbek, Tajik and Turkmen people, and the

Kenagas and Kosan Mangits have a clan with this name. Sayod//sayyot - a hunter, one engaged in hunting; is a lexeme meaning a person who organizes work related to hunting in the khan's palace, and indicates that the representatives of the sayad//sayyot clan are related to this profession.

Karovul, Turguq - these two ethnonyms are spiritually close. The Qarovul clan is found in the Yovmut Turkmen. His representatives worked as guards in Khiva and Bukhara khanates. Turguq is the name of one of the Turkic tribes. Abulghazi Bahadirkhan explains the original meaning of the word turgok as "guard", "guard".

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